

Towards Responsible Generative AI Use in EU R&I Grants: A Self-Assessment Model and the path to a Governance Framework

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Abstract

This paper explores the transformative impact of Generative AI on EU Research and Innovation (R&I) grant preparation processes. It introduces a Self-Assessment Model aimed at promoting responsible AI use while paving the way for a Governance Framework. Drawing on insights from recent surveys and guidelines, the study analyzes the widespread adoption of Generative AI tools, highlighting their benefits and challenges. With 70% of surveyed stakeholders already utilizing these tools, issues such as transparency, accountability, originality, and institutional guidance are brought to the forefront. The paper seeks to address the current lack of standardized mechanisms for AI disclosure, proposing actionable strategies to safeguard research integrity without hindering innovation.

Keywords

Generative AI, Research and Innovation (R&I), Self-Assessment Model, Governance Framework, Research Integrity, Horizon Europe, AI Disclosure, Innovation Safeguards, Ethical AI Use

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Executive Summary

Within less than three years since the first Generative AI models became available, they have spread widely across the Research and Innovation ecosystem—dramatically changing how researchers draft, refine, and structure their ideas. In the high-pressure world of competitive EU grant proposals, this shift is particularly visible. Researchers, project managers, and proposal writers increasingly turn to Generative AI tools to accelerate proposal preparation, address language and structure challenges, and navigate the complex EU policy landscape embedded in all R&I support frameworks.

Yet, as **Generative AI becomes ubiquitous in grant preparation**, important challenges emerge: How can we ensure transparency, accountability, and originality? What mechanisms can safeguard research integrity without hindering innovation? Despite a growing body of guidelines—such as those from the ERA Forum¹ and ALLEA²—there is currently **no standardized, operational model** or tools to help applicants disclose or explain the use of Generative AI during the proposal phase. This gap creates uncertainty for applicants, evaluators, and funding organisations alike.

To better understand this evolving landscape, we conducted **an anonymous survey of over 180 experienced stakeholders** involved in EU R&I grant preparation. The findings are revealing:

70% of respondents already use Generative AI tools frequently or occasionally.

25% are considering adoption.

Nearly 80% of users are reluctant to consistently disclose AI use, despite recent EU guidance requiring transparency.

The top motivations are **time savings**, while top concerns include reliability, loss of originality, hallucinated content, ethical ambiguity, and **lack of institutional guidance**.

In response, this paper proposes a **practical and actionable solution**: a **Generative AI Self-Assessment Model** for integration into **Part A of Horizon Europe IA and RIA applications**. This simple, structured template enables applicants to reflect on where and how GenAI tools were used, how their outputs were verified, and how associated risks—such as bias or IP concerns—were managed.

It is hoped that this tool can be the **first building block** of a broader **Governance Framework on Responsible Use of Generative AI in Research and Innovation (GAIRI)**. Drawing from successfully implemented regulatory frameworks like the GDPR, and Ethics Self-Assessment models, the GAIRI framework can envision an *“Integrity-by-Design”* approach that combines self-assessment, operational guidance, training, and shared standards.

¹ ERA Forum: expert group of European Commission (EC) composed of representatives of EU Member States, the EC, and R&I stakeholders

² ALLEA: European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities, representing 50+ academies from ~40 EU and non-EU countries.

1 Introduction

1.1 The rise of Generative AI in R&I and its implications

Researchers and scientists worldwide face immense pressure to successfully lead or participate in fundraising activities, alongside their core research work. This challenge is exacerbated by fierce competition and increased complexity in the funding landscape, where a deep understanding of issues related to impacts, research priorities, and their connection to broader national and transnational policy aspects is required. This environment sets the stage where the need was foreseen for the use of AI tools to support the “automation of several steps in the application and proposal preparation processes”, even before the appearance of Generative AI tools (Spyroglou et al., 2022).

The **arrival of Generative AI in 2022** through the widely accessible tools like ChatGPT took almost everyone by surprise. Up to that moment, the discussion on the transformative and revolutionary impact of AI was taking place mainly in the scientific community and certain policy domains. However, the astonishingly improved responses of these new systems created a huge wave of interest, and public discourse with sentiments ranging from anxiety and fear to rejuvenation and revelation through hype and hyperbole. (Amodei, 2024; Birhane et al., 2023; Gruetzemacher & Whittlestone, 2022; Krishna, 2024).

As AI evolved organically in the overlapping ecosystems of **science, technology, and innovation (STI)**, it was quickly integrated into the work of scientists, researchers, technologists, and innovators at various levels. This integration ranges from the purely conceptual and experimental (creative fun, brainstorming ideas) to the more practical of supporting and enhancing existing processes and methodologies (data processing, research support, literature reviews).

It is no surprise that according to a Nature’s magazine survey of 2023 close to **80% of researchers use AI in their work** (Van Noorden & Perkel, 2023). Given the pace of adoption and the continuous improvement of Generative AI tools, we can easily assume that today, 2,5 years later, this percentage is probably closer to 90% and more. These tools are leveraging the power of Machine Learning (ML) and Large Language Models (LLMs) to produce diverse forms of new content based on user instructions and while significant challenges and concerns are obvious, resisting their adoption is futile.

At the same time, the pace of recent AI developments is posing critical questions. How far are we from achieving **Superintelligence** and **Artificial General Intelligence (AGI)**, and will this be a *transformative general-purpose technology* like electricity? What will be its impact to our species? How is humanity going to adapt, protect our values and ensure prosperity? How are we going to avoid the dystopian futures we have all seen in the movies?

Despite the hype and promises, and various announcements by frontier AI labs on the speedy arrival of **AGI**, or **Superintelligence**, there is little consensus on when or even whether it will arrive (Amodei, 2024; Macaskill & Moorhouse, 2025).

Moreover, this focus on potential and real future problems can distract us from focusing on the challenges we are facing right now and undermine the necessary actions (Narayanan & Kapoor, 2025).

Without disqualifying the importance of the longer-term perspective or ignoring the ongoing discussion, this work is focusing on more **current and everyday problems and challenges** of a relative narrow audience (researchers, scientists and innovators) in the process of conceptualising, describing and justifying their ideas, in aim of research grants that will allow these ideas to turn into results.

1.2 Scope and Structure of the Paper

In this paper, we examine the *use and impact of Generative AI tools in the design and production process of research proposals*, particularly in the context of European Research and Innovation Framework Programs. To this end, we present a self-assessment model that we believe can help ensure the fair and ethical utilization of these promising new technologies. We conclude with some preliminary remarks and observations that may help define the path towards a Governance Framework. We believe that the key to success will be the co-creation of a governance framework by the actors and stakeholders themselves, rather than one that is 'dictated' by institutional processes.

The paper is structured to move from context and evidence to solution and policy recommendation.

Chapter 3 outlines the *grant application landscape* and its challenges, while chapter 4 presents the results and **insights from an original survey** on the use of Generative AI in R&I process (involving 180+ responders).

Chapter 5 investigates **Research Integrity frameworks** and how these are adapting to the Generative AI wave. It discusses the key principles, the overlaps of the different guidelines, their gaps and challenges.

Chapter 6 suggests a novel **Self-Assessment model** for documenting and justifying compliance with the Research Integrity guidelines as a first component of a **Responsible Gen AI Use in R&I Governance Framework**. Further research paths and conclusions are summarized in the final chapter along with some policy recommendations.

2 Challenges in the Current Grant Preparation Process

2.1 Complexity and Administration Burden

While innovative ideas may be endless, funding for Research and Innovation (R&I) remains limited, with demand consistently exceeding supply. The grant-winning process is **highly competitive, time-intensive**, and results are uncertain. The interim evaluation of Horizon Europe programme recognizes that the **administrative burden, fragmentation, complexity, and increased time from call deadline to grant agreement**, undermine the efficiency, effectiveness and attractiveness of the programme. A recent paper (Spyroglou et al., 2022) also highlights the growing strain researchers face in navigating increasingly complex EU funding programs and proposes the use of transdisciplinary AI systems to support semi-automation of key steps in the grant preparation process, including policy alignment and proposal drafting. Data from the first Horizon Europe period show that *the median cost of proposal preparation of (successful and unsuccessful) consortium coordinators range between 36 to 45 person-days, while consortium partners involved in the application typically spend an additional 16 to 25 person-days each. The cost of coordinators is most clearly correlated with an increase in the size of the consortium.* Given that *collaborative projects account for almost 80% of the funding under Horizon 2020 and HE, involving an average of 11 participants in nearly 15.000 projects*, the **effort invested in proposal preparation is significant**. This situation leads to a large amount of time spent on writing proposals instead of doing science (Gross & Bergstrom, 2019; Ronnlund & Duffau, 2024).

2.2 Difficulties in Policy Alignment and Impact Measurement

Researchers and proposal writers need not only have an excellent idea of the scientific concept in mind and how this can lead to a useful innovation. Reviewing the scientific soundness of their proposed intervention is not enough. They also need to study countless policy documents, guidelines, communications and decisions of European and International bodies (EU Parliament, European Commission, OECD, UN, etc.) to be able to justify alignment of their intervention with a call's expected output and anticipate its expected impact months before the project even starts. Impact measurement even after the introduction in Horizon Europe of the **Key Impact Pathways (KIPs)**, a system of indicators to capture societal impacts, remains notoriously difficult. A Report by the European Policy Analysis Group on EU Innovation Policy (Fuest et al., 2024), highlights the difficulty of judging impact especially in these early stages.

The above **challenges** are well known to EU policy makers. They are clearly acknowledged and documented in the various reports and specific improvements and measures have already been suggested. The role of Generative AI systems is also present in every single report, paper and policy of the EU: *"GenAI systems will have a major effect on how proposals are written and reviewed, how topics are selected for calls, how particular inter-or trans-disciplinary approaches might lead to new insights and how convergent areas/technologies might lead to significant innovations."* What is not certain yet is how. (Ronnlund & Duffau, 2024).

Can Generative AI (Gen AI) minimize costs of grant preparation and proposal writing? Will it increase the volume of applications while lowering their quality and originality? Will it level the field or create wider gaps and discriminations, benefiting certain organisations over others?

It is still too early to assess the full impact of Generative AI in the R&I cycle and the grant preparation process. We lack sufficient data from the post-Generative AI period to measure the volume and quality of proposals received, as well as to fully understand how researchers are applying these tools in their work. More data is needed to gain a clearer understanding of the implications.

The Role of Grants in Research and Innovation

If you are experienced with the EU Research and Innovation Frameworks and Grants you can omit this section and go to the next chapter.

The **role of innovation** in driving **economic growth and societal prosperity** is universally recognised today. Innovation is fundamentally a process born from the scientific and technological research and development (R&D). In the post-WWII era, national governments and later international organisations (like the EU) recognised their role in driving innovation and growth, establishing science and innovation strategies and policies and creating dedicated funding bodies and agencies to implement them (Edler & Fagerberg, 2017; Godin, 2006, 2015). Today, the European Commission operates numerous funding programs³ aimed at *fostering innovation, building infrastructure, and supporting its private sector*. These funding schemes—with Horizon Europe being one of the largest and most prominent—involve highly competitive, demanding, and complex application processes. (European Commission, 2025b)

In principle, the European Commission defines its priorities and policies to pursue them and allocates a budget through a 7-year multi-annual financial framework (MFF). Based on these policies, EU funding programs are created. These programs then provide implementation guidelines that determine how funded actions will be selected and carried out. For example:

A funding programme like **Horizon Europe** supports all forms of *Research and Innovation* targeting *scientific, technological, economic, environmental and societal impact*.

Digital Europe Programme “*aims to accelerate the recovery and drive the digital transformation of Europe*”.

Erasmus+ supports the “*educational, professional and personal development of people in education, training, youth and sport*”.

Figure 1: EU Grant Proposal workflow from call to grant

Each funding programme announces its priorities and expected actions through *Calls for Proposals*. Research and academic institutions (both public and private), industry players, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and—in certain programs—individual researchers can respond to these calls by *submitting proposals* that address the call requirements. These proposals undergo a *rigorous evaluation* process based on scientific merit, potential impact, and alignment with national, international, and global priorities. Those deemed successful *receive funding* and can realize their proposals and transform them into projects.

³ Funding Opportunities in EU: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities_en

3 Survey Results: How EU Grant Stakeholders use Generative AI (Gen AI)

The Nature’s survey in September 2023, provided some interesting insights into AI use in research but it did not focus on Research grant preparation (Van Noorden & Perkel, 2023). To be able to contribute to the discussion, quantify assumptions and get a better understanding of actual Generative AI (GenAI) use in grant proposal preparation, we conducted a *fully anonymous online survey on stakeholders involved in EU Grants*. The **objective** of the survey was to explore how Generative AI is used in the preparation of EU R&I proposals.

3.1 Survey Design and Participant Profile

The survey run in April 2025 and more than 180 individuals responded, all experienced stakeholders with active participation in the grant preparation process. It was created in Typeform⁴ with adaptable questions based on the responses of the participants. The survey branched out based on the response of question 5: **Do you use GenAI tools in proposal preparation?** [A. Yes, frequently | B. Yes, occasionally | C. No, but I am considering it | D. No, and I do not plan to use it] following 3 different paths and trying to identify the different behaviors and sentiments towards GenAI tools.

In case of **YES** [A|B]: Where and how participants use GenAI tools. [Q8]

In case of **NO, BUT** [C]: Why not and what would make them start using these tools. [Q6]

In case of **strict NO** [D]: Why are these stakeholders so negative and firm, about these tools. [Q7]

The chart below shows the complete logic and workflow of the survey.

Figure 2: The workflow logic behind the survey.

The graphs below show the mapping of the responders. More than 63% of the participants had over 6 years of experience in EU grants and they participated actively in the proposal preparation.

Figure 3: Role of the participant.

Figure 4: Years of experience of participants

⁴ Typeform is a platform for designing and distributing forms and collecting data (<https://www.typeform.com>).

Figure 5: Participation in proposal preparation

Figure 6: Disciplines of participants

3.2 Adoption Rates and Disclosure Pattern

According to our survey results, **70% of participants already use Generative AI tools for grant preparation** (either frequently or occasionally), and an additional **25% are considering adopting** these tools. Only less than 5% of participants stated that they **do not use** such tools and **have no plans to do so**. A revealing finding is that nearly **28% of respondents would never disclose the use of Generative AI**, while another **51.2% is more ambiguous responding that they would only sometimes** reveal their utilization of Generative AI tools. This is despite the guidelines that EC has recently (April 2025) updated the *Living guidelines on the responsible use of generative AI in research originally published in 2023* (European Commission, 2025a) and the short guidance that is provided on the Standard Application Form (HE RIA, IA) stating that “*Applicants are fully responsible for the content of the proposal (even those parts produced by the AI tool) and must be transparent in disclosing which AI tools were used and how they were utilized.*” (European Commission, 2024)

Figure 7: Use of Gen AI tools in Grant Preparation

Figure 8: Disclosure of Gen AI use in proposal preparation

These results verify our assumption that whether it is disclosed or not, the use of Generative AI tools is widely spread in the scientific community.

Figure 9: Uses of Gen AI tools by current users vs. potential users

Among frequent and occasional Generative AI users more than half utilize them for *editing and proofreading*, *summarizing documents* and *drafting proposal sections*. A deeper look shows that those not yet using Generative AI, have more scientific roles (Researcher/Scientist) rather than administrative ones (Project Manager, Proposal Writer) justifying the significance of reviewing literature for this group.

3.3 Motivation Behind Generative AI use

To explore the motives behind the use of Generative AI tools in our stakeholders, we sought to understand why participants currently use them and what would motivate those not yet using them to start. This allowed us to gain deeper insight into the driving factors behind Generative AI adoption in grant preparation.

Figure 10: Why current users use Gen AI vs. why potential users would like to use it

Time savings and managing workload is overwhelmingly (85%) the most important reason that participants use Generative AI tools. Improving the quality of the proposal, overcoming the language barriers and enhancing creativity come after.

Participants were then asked about the improvements they observed in the grant preparation process and the *quality of their proposals* after using Generative AI tools.

Figure 11: Improvement in process for existing users

Figure 12: Improvement in quality of proposal

The survey results indicate that respondents who frequently or occasionally employ Generative AI tools perceive a notable enhancement in the overall quality of their grant proposals. On a scale ranging from 0 to 10, these participants reported an average quality improvement score of 7.1. While this does not reflect a revolutionary impact, it suggests that Generative AI is generally regarded as a beneficial tool capable of enhancing the structure, clarity, and efficiency of the proposal development process.

3.4 Challenges and Concerns: Trust, Originality and Ethics

A key challenge with Generative AI tools is their lack of *reliability and accuracy* often referred to as “hallucinations”. Although these systems have improved since their initial introduction in November 2022, they can still generate surprisingly inaccurate and even fabricated results that appear correct and are accompanied by references (Bhattacharyya et al., 2023). Beyond this issue of accuracy, there are also significant *ethical concerns* around transparency, authorship, conscious or unconscious biases and fairness, as well as worries about intellectual property rights. These concerns are well-founded, and numerous reports on the challenges of AI have emphasized the urgent need for robust safeguards and responsible development practices to address these critical issues (Bjelobaba et al., 2024; Krishna, 2024).

Figure 13: Concerns by current users associated with using Gen AI tools in proposals Preparation.

In the following graphs similar concerns are expressed by participants who do not use Generative AI tools now, and either are planning to use them or claim they will not. Nonusers of Generative AI point out to lack of awareness and training signaling that further such action would probably lead them to adopt the tools in the future.

Figure 14: Concerns from non Gen AI users (Considering & Not Considering using)

Beyond the above however, a more critical challenge is apparent in **50% respondents pointing out to the loss of originality and creativity**. While Generative AI tools are convenient and save time, their outputs are not truly original. Moreover, overreliance on them can have negative effects on our cognitive abilities. A recent study by Microsoft Research Lab at Cambridge *raises questions about its impact on critical thinking skills and practices*. As users become increasingly reliant on these systems, placing trust in unverified outputs disguised by seemingly relevant but false citations, they are reducing their critical engagement and downgrading their own creativity. Prompt-following replaces ideation, and workers shift from creators to editors (Lee et al., n.d.).

3.5 The Need for Awareness and Training

Despite the overflow of information, we receive daily, most participants do not feel adequately informed about the responsible use of Generative AI in research and proposal preparation. Furthermore, they appear indifferent to the value of clear institutional or EU-level guidelines on Generative AI.

Figure 15: Level of awareness of participants on use of GenAI in R&I proposals

Figure 16: Value of clear guidelines on GenAI

The survey explored the need for training on responsible Generative AI use. Over **80% of participants reported receiving little to no training in this area**. The most pressing training needs identified were technical instruction on the tools, guidance on legal implications, and ethical guidelines for their use.

Figure 17: Participants that have received training

Figure 18: Training topics that responders believe beneficial

3.6 Future Expectations

The final survey question aimed to gather a more quantitative perspective on how participants foresee the evolution of Generative AI tools over the next 3-5 years. Specifically, they were asked: "*Do you believe Generative AI will become a standard practice in EU grant preparation within the next 3-5 years?*" The median response rating for this question was 9, indicating a near-universal belief that AI will play a significant role in various aspects of the research and innovation process, including the grant preparation stage.

Figure 19: How strongly participants believe Gen AI will become standard practice

3.7 The Insights

Beyond the raw data and the obvious insights summarized below, the whole process allowed some interesting observations. For instance: *80% of the responses were collected within 3 days* and more than 20 people emailed back with an explicit request to stay informed and receive the results. This proves the interest of all stakeholders involved in the process in learning more about Generative AI and how their colleagues use it.

The data suggests the rise of GenAI in grant preparation is undeniable, with timesaving and quality enhancement being primary drivers. Still there is a significant problem of distrust, accompanied by ethical and integrity concerns. There is clearly an expressed need for support, training, clear guidance, and case studies to address these challenges. This section summarizes the key insights from the survey.

GenAI Adoption is already widespread

71.8% of participants have already integrated the use of Generative AI in their grant preparation process either frequently or occasionally.

Still, a *significant percentage (28.2%) remains hesitant*, mainly due to low trust, ethical concerns, lack of awareness or any combination of these.

Only a *very small group is still resisting* (9 out of 181 participants – 5%) and declares no interest or willingness to explore Gen AI tools. However, even in their case they report the same problems as the ‘hesitant’ group.

GenAI Adds real value to grant preparation

The *strongest reason and motivation* for using Generative AI tools *is saving time (84%)*.

Improving the quality of the language comes second.

Enhancing creativity and innovation comes higher for those that are not using Gen AI (46,7%) vs. those who do (36,2%). The sample may be too small for a safe conclusion, however, could the reason be the realisation that Generative AI tools are not so original or creative after all?⁵

Only 1.7% reported no improvement in their work, and overall quality improvement scored 7/10, reflecting strong perceived effectiveness.

Trust, Ethical and Legal uncertainty are a major barrier

Among both users and non-users, the top concerns include *Lack of trust in the accuracy and reliability of the results (65,5%)*.

Ethical Issues (Transparency and authorship) end up second with 53,4%.

More than 50% points out to the *loss of originality and creativity* an issue that some reports already point out (see *Challenges and Concerns* above)

Lack of training and institutional guidance hampers responsible use

Only 20% of respondents feel fully informed on responsible AI use.

62% have received no training at all on responsible GenAI use.

Despite high usage, most rely on trial-and-error, raising risks of misuse or inconsistency.

There is *no consensus on disclosure*, with more than half only disclosing "sometimes" or "never."

Strong demand exists for structured support: Technical training (66%), Legal guidance (64%), Ethical frameworks (60%).

Standardized Frameworks Are Needed—and Wanted

The *lack of policy clarity* and institutional rules creates a grey zone.

Respondents signal *clear support for guidelines*, especially if they improve trust, privacy and confidentiality.

The current *absence of formal standards* risks exacerbating inequalities, giving an edge to better-resourced institutions or aggressive adopters.

GenAI Is Here to Stay—and Policy Must Catch Up

Respondents rate the likelihood of *Generative AI becoming standard practice* in EU grants in 3–5 years at 8.2/10.

The *ecosystem is moving faster than the rules*, leaving gaps in ethics, fairness, and review mechanisms.

Without intervention, inconsistencies in use and disclosure could affect both proposal quality and evaluation integrity.

This survey reveals a growing reliance on GenAI in EU grant preparation, accompanied by clear benefits and significant risks. Researchers need **clear, harmonized, and enforceable guidance**—not only to unlock GenAI's full potential, but to ensure its **responsible, fair, and transparent use** in a highly competitive funding landscape.

A clear framework on the **responsible use of Generative AI tools** is urgently needed, focusing explicitly on the R&I grant process. This framework should be supported by implementation tools, templates, and training, and should be aligned with the EC's and international policies on AI, adopting at the same time the most current recommendations for a radical simplification of the overall grant application process (Ronnlund & Duffau, 2024).

⁵ It is possible that as users gain experience with these tools, they come to recognize the limitations in terms of true originality and creativity. Further research with a larger sample would be needed to draw more definitive conclusions on this point.

4 Existing Research Integrity and Generative AI use guidelines

4.1 The Evolution of Research Integrity Frameworks

The concept of **Research Integrity** was introduced by Charles Babbage, a philosopher, mathematician, engineer and inventor back in the 19th century. It became relevant with in the late 1970s when several fraud scandals in biomedical research in the US attracted high profile public attention (White, 2004). Since then, research institutions and policy makers formalized definitions on scientific misconduct and produced ethics codes and guidelines for research practice. Among the key such documents and initiatives are:

German Research Foundation (DFG) “*Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice*” (1998). These guidelines were among the very first comprehensive national rules in Europe setting a model on transparent research procedures and detailing standards for authorship, data retention, supervision, and the investigation of misconduct. Updated (2019): “*Code of Conduct: Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice*” with strengthened whistle-blower protections and clarified responsibilities for all research actors. (Forschungsgemeinschaft, 2019)

European Commission “*European Charter for Researchers*” & “*Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers*” (2005, 2023) Introduced a shared understanding of researcher integrity within Europe’s “*open labor market for researchers.*” (European Charter for Researchers and on a Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers, 2005)

ALLEA (All European Academies) “*European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity*” (2011, 2017, 2023). The Code promoted four foundational principles (**reliability, honesty, respect, accountability**) and detailed good practice guidelines covering data management, publication, authorship, supervision, and misconduct procedures. In 2017 Open Science was added. The 2023 edition addressed challenges from digital infrastructures (including AI) and GDPR compliance. (ALLEA, 2023)

Science Europe “*Fostering Research Integrity in Europe*” *Roadmap* (2016). Identified gaps in procedures and called for harmonized, cross-border frameworks and mutual recognition of integrity standards. (European Science Foundation, 2010)

The key principles of Research Integrity serve as the starting point for creating a **reliable, foundational framework** for the responsible use of Generative AI in Research and Innovation including the grant preparation process. These key principles should be reflected in every aspect of scientific and research work.

Table 1: Key principles of Research Integrity

Honesty	Remain transparent, open and honest in all aspects of research work, including attributing contributions, communicating goals and intentions transparently, reporting methods and procedures clearly, and justifying their assumptions and interpretations in a fair and unbiased manner.
Reliability and Rigor	Conduct research with high professionalism and rigor to guarantee quality, reliability, and robustness. Follow standards, ensure quality assurance throughout the research process. Rigorously question all findings, verifying results and allow easy replication.
Respect and Care	Show respect and care for colleagues, research participants, research subjects (human, animal, cultural, biological, environmental, or physical), society, ecosystems, cultural heritage, and the environment.
Accountability and Responsibility	Be accountable for research, from initial idea to publication, management, organization, training, supervision, mentoring, and wider societal impacts. Comply with standards, and institutional guidelines. Be objective, impartial and independent of conflicting interests.

A simple glimpse at all these documents will show that a lot of the principles and guidelines overlap and are often interconnected. New concepts and ideas were incorporated like ethics commitments, the **FAIR principles** (*Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable*) of Open Science, Diversity, equality and inclusiveness.

4.2 AI Guidelines in EU

As Generative AI were introduced and AI research took the front stage, all the above organisations have updated their guidelines to include more specific instructions on how researchers should address the various challenges of AI. In addition, new guidelines and policy documents appeared:

Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI (2019). Issued by the EU High-Level Expert Group on AI. It defined seven key requirements for trustworthy AI including human agency, transparency, and accountability AI in Science in EU.

ALTAI: Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (2020). A self-assessment tool expanding on the Ethics Guidelines and operationalized their recommendations for organisations using AI.

Ethics by Design and Ethics of Use Approaches for AI (2021). Published under Horizon Europe to guide researchers developing or using AI, including robotics. Emphasized fundamental rights, human oversight, and data governance AI in Science in EU.

ALLEA's Revised European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (2023). Updated to reflect advances in AI, Open Science, and the importance of responsible research cultures. It sets out principles such as reliability, honesty, respect, and accountability.

AI in Science in the EU – Scientific Opinion (March 2024). An extensive report assessing how to foster responsible uptake of AI in science, highlighting regulatory gaps, challenges in integrating generative AI, and the necessity of trustworthy AI ecosystems AI in Science in EU.

ERA Forum Guidelines (2024, April 2025). A living document offering specific recommendations for researchers, research organisations, and funding bodies on the responsible use of generative AI in research, with emphasis on integrity, transparency, and accountability. (European Commission, 2025a)

4.3 Living guidelines on the responsible use of generative AI in research (ERA Forum)

Generative AI is the latest addition to this work. ERA Forum, an expert group of the European Commission composed of representatives of EU Member States, the European Commission, and R&I stakeholders, published a key document with guidelines on using Generative AI in research. The document is applicable to researchers, research institutions and funding organisations from both the public and private sector. The document first appeared in March 2024 and was updated again in April 2025 (European Commission, 2025a). The document makes 6 recommendations for researchers, aligned with the key principles of research integrity.

Table 2: Key Recommendations for Researchers in ERA Forum Stakeholders' Guidelines

Accountability and Integrity	<i>KNOW</i> . Be aware and recognize biases, “hallucination” and invented citations. <i>OWN</i> all AI-generated text - <i>NO AI authorship</i> .
Transparency and Disclosure	<i>DISCLOSE</i> Gen AI Use clearly in proposal drafting, data processing or other use. <i>AVOID MISREPRESENTATION</i> . Do not present AI-generated text as original human-authored insights without review or editing.
Privacy, confidentiality and IPR	<i>PROTECT</i> confidential data and sensitive work. <i>DO NOT UPLOAD</i> or reveal Personal Data. <i>DO NOT DISCLOSE</i> proprietary or intellectually protected information.
Regulatory and Legal Compliance	<i>RESPECT</i> national, EU and international regulations and laws. <i>RESPECT</i> authorship, proper recognition of work and citation. <i>APPLY</i> FAIR Open Science principles where possible.

AI Literacy	<i>STAY INFORMED</i> and continuously develop your AI skills. <i>LEARN</i> to recognize biases, hallucinations, and scope limitations of GenAI tools. <i>EVALUATE</i> and <i>SELECT</i> the most appropriate tool for the work
Appropriate Use	<i>AVOID</i> using Gen AI tools substantially especially in sensitive activities (Evaluation, assessment of work)

Are Generative AI Guidelines enough?

While the above guidelines are clear, they often overlap and remain generic. They do not suggest concrete steps to follow, they do not offer any templates or checklists as starting points, and they do not define clear assessment criteria for compliance.

Currently, there is **no standardized or mandated process** across major funding bodies for documenting Generative AI use in grant preparation. As of the time of writing (April 2025) that is **no formal requirement** from major funders like the European Commission, UKRI, NSF, or NIH to declare Generative AI use in proposals. Journals and publishers (e.g., Nature, Elsevier) are beginning to require AI usage disclosures following the same trends toward transparency, accountability, and integrity in research workflows. Emerging good practices and early guidance are being developed but are still purely adopted.

We believe that in addition to guidelines a more complete framework is needed that will include not only the guidelines but the necessary templates, checklists, best practices and training modules that will ensure the effective and responsible use of Generative AI tools.

5 Towards a Governance Framework for Responsible Generative AI Use

5.1 Proposal for a GenAI Self-Assessment Model

Using Horizon Europe as an example we analyse the application form for IA and RIA⁶ proposals, identify some weak points and suggest some improvements that will guide researchers in the process and eliminate the ambiguities. Currently, the Horizon Europe proposal structure involves two main parts:

Part A (Administrative): Information auto-generated by IT systems, largely quantitative and structural.

Part B (Narrative): Detailed narrative sections directly linked to evaluation criteria (Excellence, Impact, and Implementation), manually written by applicants and assessed by evaluators.

The Horizon Europe Programme Standard Application Form (HE RIA, IA) initially addressed AI on September 2022 in version 3.1 and added a new section with guidance on the use of AI in preparation.

Version	Publication date	Changes
3.1	08.09.2022	Added instructions on Artificial Intelligence
3.3	27.09.2023	Guidance on the use of AI for the preparation of the proposal

Ethics and Security Section: The ethics table added the question: "*Does this activity involve the development, deployment, and/or use of Artificial Intelligence-based systems?*" In case of a positive response, applicants must detail ethical concerns related to human rights and values and explain how these will be addressed.

Guidance on the use of generative AI tools for proposal preparation: The newest version of the Application form (v3.3), includes some guidance on the use of Generative AI tools for the preparation of the proposal. These are in line with the research integrity principles asking for ownership, accuracy, transparency, accountability.

Table 3: Guidance on the use of Gen AI tools in the HE Standard Application Form (IA, RIA)

Guidance on the use of generative AI tools for the preparation of the proposal
<p>When considering the use of generative artificial intelligence (AI) tools for the preparation of the proposal, it is imperative to exercise caution and careful consideration. The AI-generated content should be thoroughly reviewed and validated by the applicants to ensure its appropriateness and accuracy, as well as its compliance with intellectual property regulations. Applicants are fully responsible for the content of the proposal (even those parts produced by the AI tool) and must be transparent in disclosing which AI tools were used and how they were utilized.</p> <p>Specifically, applicants are required to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verify the accuracy, validity, and appropriateness of the content and any citations generated by the AI tool and correct any errors or inconsistencies. • Provide a list of sources used to generate content and citations, including those generated by the AI tool. Double-check citations to ensure they are accurate and properly referenced. • Be conscious of the potential for plagiarism where the AI tool may have reproduced substantial text from other sources. Check the original sources to be sure you are not plagiarizing someone else's work. • Acknowledge the limitations of the AI tool in the proposal preparation, including the potential for bias, errors, and gaps in knowledge.

Nevertheless, and despite this new section on Guidance the strict page limits of the Technical Part of the application (30 pages in most programs) and the rather vague expectations make it very hard for proposers to be fully compliant. This was apparent also from our survey responses where approximately *3 out of 10 researchers would never disclose Gen AI use and half of them are hesitant*, judging on case per case.

⁶ Innovation Actions (IA) focus on prototyping, demonstrating and validating new products or services at TRL 5-8. Research and Innovation Actions (RIAs) support R&D for new technologies at TRL 3-6.

Even if researchers explain how Generative AI is used, this justification is arbitrary and will be almost lost in the narrative section (Part B) and might be easily missed by the evaluators. Furthermore, now there is no clear repercussions for not reporting the use of Generative AI tools raising concerns of fairness and transparency.

To remedy the above issues, it is critical to move this requirement from Part B to Part A, adding a clear and concise “*Declaration of GenAI Use*” section with explicit questions and predefined drop-down options that will enforce a minimum degree of standardization. This section should be mandatory with “Yes/No” questions regarding the use of Generative AI tools in proposal writing. In case of a positive response, applicants will be requested to provide information on the following:

Tools Used: Identification of the specific GenAI tools employed (e.g., ChatGPT, Gemini, Claude etc.).

Purpose and extent of use: A detailed description of how each tool was utilized in the grant preparation process, including the specific tasks for which it was employed.

Content Generation: For creating text, figures, or other elements of the proposal.

Data Analysis: Assisting in the analysis of data relevant to the proposal.

Literature Review: For summarizing existing research and identifying relevant sources.

Human Oversight: An explanation of the measures taken to ensure human review and validation of AI-generated content, addressing issues of accuracy, bias, and intellectual property compliance.

The above questions are indicative and need to be further discussed during a design and pilot evaluation of such implementation. Such a declaration can have the status of a formal statement by the coordinator or principal investigator, affirming the accuracy and completeness of the information provided. This approach not only promotes transparency but also ensures that the use of Generative AI is systematically considered and addressed, enhancing the overall integrity and credibility of the grant application process. Although one might think that this approach complicates the process and adds an extra level of bureaucracy and administration burden, we believe that the benefits outweigh the drawbacks. The approach ensures:

Structured Transparency

By placing disclosure requirements in Part A, applicants are explicitly reminded of their responsibility to declare GenAI use early and clearly.

Structured self-assessment forms promote standardization, simplifying evaluators' tasks to easily check GenAI usage.

Consistent Compliance

A standardized self-assessment, much like the Ethics Self-Assessment, ensures uniformity of information across all proposals, facilitating consistent and objective reviews.

It allows funders to easily verify that applicants have consciously and explicitly addressed the ethical and accuracy-related aspects of GenAI use.

Aligns with EU guidelines and the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.

No Conflict with Page Limits

Researchers currently omit GenAI disclosures partly due to limited page allowances in Part B. Shifting disclosures to Part A completely removes this pressure, as Part A does not contribute to the strict narrative page limits.

Improved Proposal Evaluation

Evaluators will have easier access to this essential compliance-related information, allowing them to focus their evaluation on scientific quality, innovation, and feasibility in Part B.

Encouraging Accountability and Responsible Use of GenAI

A dedicated self-assessment increases awareness of GenAI's limitations (e.g., bias, accuracy issues), promoting responsible and informed use by applicants.

5.2 Suggested Structure for a GenAI Self-Assessment in Part A

The below suggestions are provided merely as a starting point on how the “**Generative AI Use Self-Assessment**” could be built and should be viewed as a first draft, rather than a fully fleshed-out solution. It is following the successful format of the Ethics Self-Assessment, which is a mandatory questionnaire in Part A, and aims to provide a more structured, transparent, and standardized approach to documenting the use of GenAI in grant proposals, enhancing the integrity and credibility of the research and innovation funding process. The survey has 10 questions combining check boxes selection with free text responses. Low character limits are applied to incentivize short and to-the-point answers.

A disclaimer added to encourage truthful and complete responses by assuring applicants that their answers will not influence the evaluation of their proposals. It helps reduce fear of bias or penalty, clarifies that the purpose is learning—not judgment—and supports the development of realistic, evidence-based policies. By fostering a safe environment for disclosure, the disclaimer promotes transparency, enables better guidance for future applicants, and contributes to a responsible research culture.

Generative AI Use Self-Assessment (Part A)

1. Did you use Generative AI tools (e.g., GPT models, Bard, Claude, etc.) in preparing your proposal?

YES	NO (if no, skip to declaration)
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2. If YES, specify clearly which GenAI tools you used and briefly describe how each was utilized.

Open-ended with limited characters	<i>ChatGPT (4.0 – Apr 2025) – Brainstorming research questions, improving language and clarity, generate a first draft of the impact section.</i>
Example:	<i>NotebookLM (Mar – Apr 2025) – Summarizing and analyzing papers and policies</i> <i>Elicit (Mar 2025) – Literature Review on Climate Change Models.</i>

3. How have you verified and ensured accuracy and reliability of AI-generated content (including claims, justifications and references)?

Check Box Selection	<input type="checkbox"/> Cross-checked against primary sources <input type="checkbox"/> Reviewed by human expert(s)	<input type="checkbox"/> Used citation/reference checking tools <input type="checkbox"/> Used plagiarism detection software <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
Example:	<i>All AI-generated sections were checked against peer-reviewed articles. Mendeley used to verify references, Turnitin for plagiarism screening.</i>	

4. How did you check for and address potential plagiarism or copyright issues?

Check Box Selection	<input type="checkbox"/> Used plagiarism detection software (e.g., Turnitin, iThenticate) <input type="checkbox"/> Manually compared with source materials <input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable (no AI-generated content used)
Example:	<i>Turnitin report showed 5% similarity, mostly references on EU policy documents. Adjustments made to remove close paraphrasing and explicit references were added.</i>

5. Have all citations produced by GenAI been manually reviewed and verified?

Check Box Selection	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input type="checkbox"/> No <i>(if Partially or No explain why)</i>
Example:	<i>Yes, all references were verified using PubMed and Google Scholar. Two hallucinated citations were removed.</i>	

6. Did you input any sensitive, confidential, or personal data into GenAI tools?

Check Box Selection	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <i>(with appropriate safeguards and/or consent)</i>
Example:	<i>Yes, internal project summaries were shared Mistral AI hosted on a secure, enterprise server with team consent.</i>

7. Have you addressed potential biases, limitations, or hallucinations in AI-generated content?

Check Box Selection	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <i>(Briefly explain how these risks were considered and mitigated)</i>
Example:	<i>All prompts were carefully reviewed to avoid biases, actively trying to eliminate any preposition. Critical questions were repeated to ensure replicability of the responses.</i>

8. Did you receive input or review from colleagues, mentors, or supervisors on AI-generated content?

Check Box Selection	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes
Example:	<i>Two senior researchers reviewed all sections drafted with AI and provided edits to ensure accuracy.</i>

9. Are you aware of your institutional (or other EU, international) policy guidelines in the use of Gen AI in your grant preparation?

Check Box Selection	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes. Policy guidelines were followed. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, but unsure about full compliance. <input type="checkbox"/> No, not aware of such policies. <i>(Briefly explain how these risks were considered and mitigated)</i>
Example:	<i>The ERA's Forum Living Guidelines were used as a basis for compliance.</i>

10. Did the use of GenAI impact your proposal writing process (positively or negatively)?

Check Box Selection	<input type="checkbox"/> Positive. Improved time. <input type="checkbox"/> Positive. Improved quality.	<input type="checkbox"/> Neutral. No major change. <input type="checkbox"/> Negative. It created issues.
	<i>(Briefly explain how these risks were considered and mitigated)</i>	
Example:	<i>Positive: Helped structure ideas more clearly and reduced writing time by ~30%.</i>	

Disclaimer on Use of Generative AI Self-Assessment Responses

All applicants are expected to comply with **Research Integrity guidelines**, including those concerning transparency, authorship, accuracy, and the responsible use of AI tools.

However, your responses to these **self-assessment questions will not be used in the technical evaluation** of your proposal. They are not part of the eligibility criteria and will have no influence on the funding decision.

We kindly ask you to answer these questions truthfully and thoughtfully. Your input will help us better understand how Generative AI tools are being used in proposal development and improve future guidance and support for applicants.

Thank you for your cooperation in fostering transparency and responsible innovation.

5.3 Limitations and Future Research

While our research offers interesting insights, the scope was relatively narrow, and important aspects were omitted or intentionally ignored. These limitations and unexplored aspects can serve as research paths for the future.

Quantification of Generative AI Tool Usage

A major limitation is that there isn't enough reliable data on how much Generative AI is used during grant writing. The current survey grouped people into broad categories but didn't measure exactly how they use AI. Future studies should track into more detail how often and in what ways researchers use AI (like daily use, use in different parts of a proposal, or how heavily they rely on it) to better understand how much Generative AI is really part of research and innovation proposal writing.

Understanding Biases mechanisms

The paper only briefly mentions the problems with Generative AI, like biases, mistakes, and hallucinations, and doesn't explain how to deal with them in a clear way. Future research should look into creating standard tools or review methods to help researchers use Generative AI more safely and reliably.

Proposal Quality and Simplification of R&I Processes

This research has not looked closely at important problems caused by using Generative AI, like the risk of many low-quality AI-generated applications flooding the system. It is important to study how Generative AI affects the quality of proposals, the workload for reviewers, and the fairness of evaluations. Also, future work should examine how Generative AI fits into the "radical simplification" idea mentioned in the Interim Evaluation report of Horizon Europe. The recommendations of the report explicitly call for the investigation and implementation of use of AI to massively increase the efficiency of application and review process. (Ronnlund & Duffau, 2024)

Cover the whole lifecycle of Research and Innovation

In this paper we explored Generative AI tools during the grant preparation phase. Although there is an explicit guideline to exclude AI systems from the evaluation and review process, we may be able to utilize them for some aspects of it, like the eligibility check or the drafting of the evaluation report. Moreover, the use and impact of Generative and AI is not limited to the initial stages of R&I (application and selection of ideas). It transcends the full lifecycle of the project, utilized throughout its implementation. The Research Integrity framework applies to these stages as well and we can use best practices as we have done in the past with the Data Management Plan to govern the use of Generative AI throughout the life of the project.

Integration with EU AI Act

The impact of the EU AI Act into the R&I contexts has not been fully explored. Further research must address how the AI Act's regulatory requirements will intersect with existing R&I practices, identifying specific obligations and adjustments needed by stakeholders to ensure compliance.

These limitations and unexplored aspects show areas for future research on the responsible and effective use of Generative AI tools in R&I.

These gaps show where more research is needed to explore the responsible and efficient use of Generative AI in research and innovation. We recognize these as the main limits of our current study and hope that further discussion will identify additional limitations that we can then investigate.

5.4 Towards a Framework for Generative AI use for R&I (GAIRI)

Generative AI has the power to change research and innovation by boosting productivity, creativity, and access. But it also brings big challenges, like ethical problems, data privacy risks, and threats to research integrity. A new **Framework for Generative AI Use in Research & Innovation (GAIRI)** could help tackle these issues in a clear and organized way, making sure AI is used responsibly and transparently in the EU's research ecosystem.

The proposed **Self-Assessment Model** could help organize and improve the process, offering valuable insights, but it's not enough by itself. The survey clearly shows that there is a strong need for tools, clear information, and training on all parts of Generative AI use — from how to use it properly to understanding ethics and governance.

The Self-Assessment Model and template should just be the starting point. From there, we can build a full Governance Framework for AI use in Research & Innovation. Starting with a challenge-focused approach and clear, common definitions, this framework can create a foundation for accountability and integrity. It could offer practical tools like checklists, standard procedures (SOPs), templates, and training programs to help ensure compliance. We can also learn from success stories like Privacy and GDPR efforts, or initiatives such as the World Conferences on Research Integrity⁷, CoARA⁸, or “Privacy by Design”⁹.

Objectives of the Framework for Generative AI Use for Research & Innovation (GAIRI)

GAIRI should be designed to provide clear guidance, practical tools, and standardized mechanisms to ensure:

Transparency and **accountability** in the use of generative AI.

Compliance with ethical standards and legal regulations, including the EU AI Act and GDPR.

Promotion of **research integrity** and **trustworthiness** in AI applications.

Capacity building of researchers' skills through targeted training and awareness initiatives.

Reduction of administrative burdens and complexity in R&I processes through innovative AI-driven simplifications.

A European AI-on-demand Platform

The promise of an AI-on-demand platform by EU “*to facilitate access to all potential users... to the latest technologies and encourage them to test AI*” was suggested in one of the earliest documents on AI for Europe but so far has not been realized. (Artificial Intelligence for Europe, 2018). A platform built with European technology and infrastructure would be a major step forward, offering reliable, secure, and GDPR-compliant Generative AI tools for research and innovation grant preparation. If developed, the proposed framework could become its Governance backbone.

⁷ World Conferences on Research Integrity Foundation (WCRIF) is a non-profit Organisation promoting Research Integrity. [<https://www.wcrif.org>]

⁸ CoARA: Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) is a collective of organisations committed to reforming the evaluations methods and processes of research, researchers, and research organisations.

⁹ Privacy by Design is a methodology for proactively embedding privacy into information technology, business practices, and networked infrastructures developed originally by the Information and Privacy commissioner of Ontario, Canada.

6 Conclusions

Generative AI (GenAI) is quickly changing the EU's research and innovation ecosystem, offering increased creativity and productivity. At the same time, it brings serious ethical, legal, and practical challenges. This paper looked at how Generative AI is currently used in EU grant processes, based on a survey of stakeholders. The results show that more people are turning to GenAI, mainly to save time, work more efficiently, and improve the quality of grant proposals.

But using Generative AI also brings big concerns about transparency, trust, originality, and integrity. It raises questions about authorship, intellectual property, and ethical compliance. The lack of clear rules from institutions and funders makes things even more uncertain for researchers and reviewers.

To help address these issues, this paper suggests a Generative AI Self-Assessment Model and a future Governance Framework for Generative AI in Research and Innovation (GAIRI). These aim to create standard rules for disclosure, set clear methods for checking AI content, improve researchers' understanding of AI, and align with broader EU policies on AI and research integrity.

If used wisely, Generative AI could help Europe become even more competitive globally. But it must be done carefully. The EU must balance innovation and regulation by building simple, reliable, safe, and flexible governance frameworks that protect quality and safety without slowing down progress.

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